

Morality

I begin this report by saying little about myself. My perspective of Morality is from a neutral ground of Defined Logic and Science. As Spirituality and conventional belief system makes no sense to me, So I try to uncover the world analytically by giving some objective base value to every subjective decisions we make.

There is no single agreed upon definition for the term “moral” in the psychological literature. However, as a practical point of departure, let us make use of an adapted version of a dictionary definition: morality consists of the rules of conduct based on conscience or the sense of right and wrong.

Early philosophers and Social influencer had little critical sense, they were blindly accepting dogmatic premises in their consideration of morality. In reality morality is a dynamic term, it changes its meaning and principles continuously as the society progress. A pragmatic perspective is needed to understand morality and good and evil for that matter.

Now, coming to Good and Evil, these words although may have some apparent meaning to it but a deep analysis on this would result in redeeming this words as meaningless. Human society even in this century works on the age old principle of story telling. From childhood we are constantly being manipulated as to grow more suitable personality to adopt with the set norms of the society. And for this we are constantly fed informations and do's and don'ts in the head of such believes that sometimes contradicts with each other. Children in the early age are taught, Killing is bad, hurting is bad, but then in almost every country, they are sung the songs of the Heroes of the nation. They are fed the stories of how the Freedom Fighters murdered the colonizers and rid the nation of them. Here the Killing incident is presented as good thing to the children. As little consciousness children have, their state of

mind at some point of time witnesses a conflict within themselves as when to deem something as Good or Evil.

We as a society have only created fabricated lies around us to make our meaningless lives seem important to some extent. The stories are so strong that it could lead someone to give up their lives happily as to apparent important but baseless causes like Nationalism or Crusades. Morals without intervening of logic is superstitions. Soldiers are made to think their death is for the greater good of the nation, when the concept of nation itself has no objective truth to it. There is no borders on earth when seen from space, the imaginary borders that now exist will be altered in future and thus deeming the death of a brave soldier more meaningless.

Simple humans by what I define them as, reluctant to critical thinking, are more prone to hold up a belief just at the face value. They are happy to encapsulate their world in a small subsection of around them, they find meaning of their existence in the community they are living in. Their morals values reflects the apparent good and bad outcomes of their community. The stories indeed work, cause everyone believes it works, So when a conflict arises on national level, believers of one story justifies doing bad things to the other believers as National duty and same thing happens in the other side as well, and thus this concept of Dynamic Morality works.

If we level down a bit into our personal space for a while, then also it becomes clear as what this stories contribute to hold up the image and structure of the society. A hypocrisy is seen when regarding some as High Society and low society for what comes from an even disruptive use of morality. If we let loose all the moral norms of the society then we won't be able to comprehend the human world anymore. Its the basic morality we are taught in the schools in early ages that says killing someone is bad that keeps us confident in the streets even after decades, that no one in their right mind will kill us.

Another aspect of morality comes in sexual conflicts. Thousand years ago greek philosopher Sophocles wrote about King Oedipus and his tragic ending.

This was a highly acclaimed piece of literature but it had a hidden agenda as well, that is to set a social norm or encouraging a moral value, that will keep us humans from engaging into incest relationships. As Freud had pointed out that our first sexual desire arises for the very first person we love from the early childhood. Puberty hurts because we go through a conflict of love and physical desires at the age. The Society enforces this moral very strongly not to indulge in incest relationships so we look for the traits of them in our future life companions. Social learning theorists have demonstrated convincingly that children imitate social models' prosocial and aggressive behaviors, and there is abundant evidence for the conditioning of anxiety. However, the learning approach has had difficulty in accounting for other moral feelings (shame and guilt) or for age-related changes in moral reasoning and judgment.

Piaget and Kohlberg's research shows that other than social norms, Cognitive developments also produce in morality, that moral reasoning, based on the concepts of equality and reciprocity, changes in predictable ways across the years of childhood and youth. Evolutionary psychologists however have pointed evidence from ethological studies that reciprocity in prosocial behavior confers selective advantages in a group-living species, particularly when combined with a tendency to punish defections. So as to grow strong as a cult and survive in natural selection this adaptive behaviors or morals are necessary.

Although modern evolutionary biologists claim that our feelings are side products of cognitive analysis of a situation in terms of probability of best fit outcomes. And this actually gives an entire new field of vision to look into while taking a moral decision. Rage is considered a bad thing in every moral lectures but modern science explains it as our natural reflex to some uncomfortable situation that one think should not prevail. Suppressing anger just because it is a bad trait is not perhaps the best thing to do in a situation, but how one point the rage and control their actions while in an excited state is something very important. Every anger that emerges has a very prominent reason behind it, although it should be noted that extremism is not to be confused with anger.

Religions and Politics have played a major role in popularizing several morals in the masses. Best examples are like Nationalism and Forgiveness. It is considered dying for the nation is a good thing to do. Dostoevsky had once told Dying is the least special thing one can do, to live with a determined spirit to ensure a victory is much more difficult. As well as forgiving others for their 'sins' is considered a good thing to do. German Philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche pointed out in 19th century the moral deformities in masses are largely enforced by the practice of religions. The slave society in Roman Empire was a perfect plot for promoting a religion. Religions bended people according to its self-interests and their most powerful tool was provoking false sense of morality in the slaves. Slaves in every country those days were denied basic human rights, yet they did not have the stomach to fight against the system. The aristocrats wanted to have all the good possessions to themselves and that would not have been possible if the poor and middle class had revolted. So they very intelligently promoted this made up morals like, Sexlessness is Purity, Weakness is Goodness, Submission to a animal of same species without any reason is termed as Obedience and Not being able to take revenge is termed as Forgiveness. Religion is indeed the opiate of the masses.

But, coming to the 21st century still there are elements in the society that encourages false morality. Social media platforms and the social trends are the opiate of this century, where more likes, upvotes and dislikes, downvotes are becoming the new measurements of good and evil, when most of the times this actions are done from momentary emotional urges.

In the context, another thing should be brought in, that is the rise of Data-centric decision taking abilities. Or the fundamental basis of Modern day and as well as Future of Morality. Nowadays, we have easy access to data, factoids and informations that enables us to analyze the outcomes better before committing any decision. Well while taking a certain moral decision Respecting everyone's opinion to an extent is considered polite but if we ask the Talibans on what their social stand on humanity or if we ask the Somalians to how to run a country then, some of us have to agree that we are better off denying "some" people's opinions on morality. It is possible for an individual or a whole culture to care about the wrong things. As of now the

world is filled with nuclear weapons, biohazards, AI weapons and other destructive elements. There are more and more things that would ground the societies as we know within seconds. The destruction from a Nuclear explosion doesn't care about our made up stories of Nations and borders, a nuclear war will simply eliminate the entire human civilization.

The time has come that our stories need to be refreshed, as globalization becoming more and more prominent each day, we have to set morals in the benefits of entire human civilization. It seems to be therefore, patently obvious that we can no more respect and tolerate vast differences in notions of human well-being than we can respect or tolerate vast differences in the notions about how disease spreads, or in the safety standards of buildings and airplanes. We simply must converge on the answers we give to the most important questions in human life.

Questions of morality are becoming more and more important this days as to the rise of Artificial Intelligence. If a driverless car roams the street and in a critical corner comes a child in front, avoiding the child could endanger the passengers in it, now the question comes, Should the car continue on its path, ensuring its passengers' safety at the child's expense?

Or lets take the classic question of moral dilemma, If you are in a situation where you have to choose between, the one person you love the most in the world and thousand unknown people in a Life or Death situation, who will you choose? What will be the morally right thing to do?

If you want to sacrifice the one person to save thousands then you are wrong, each day thousands of people die you don't care then why now? How could you sacrifice someone who loves you?

If on the other hand, you choose to save the one person matters to you, then you directly being the cause of thousand people's death and that would be a selfish act.

Murdering one or many innocents, both are equal offense but if you choose to save the one then you are Letting the others die and if you choose the others then you are Killing the one.

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